

DIFFICULTIES FACED BY PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN ACTIVITY BASED LEARNING (ABL)

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Abstract:

Education in India was through the Gurukul system up to a few centuries ago till the beginning of British rule in India. But in this Activity Based Learning (ABL) method transaction to the primary schools, teachers faced lot of problems. So the vestigator has identified the teachers working in the primary schools situated in cuddalore district as sample. Hence, the researcher has made an attempt to study the problems faced in activity based learning of the primary school teachers. The objectives of this study is to find study the level of Difficulties faced by primary school teaches in Activity Based Learning and the significance of the difference between the following of sub-samples with respect to their difficulties faced in Activity Based leering. The following tool has been used for collecting data. Problems faced in ABL scale standardized by K. Muruganantham (2010). It is taken from the school register. The tool was administered to a random sample of 250 primary school teachers working in the cuddalore education district. The scoring of the tool has been done according to the instructions given in the manual. The data has been subjected to statistical techniques like descriptive analysis and differential analysis. The result showed that Difficulties faced in ABL of primary school teachers is average. Male and female primary school teachers do not differ significantly in their Difficulties faced in ABL. Samples belonging to differ in their nature of family do not differ significantly in their Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning. Subjects who belong to upto 30 years and above 30 years differ significantly in their Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning.

Key Words: Difficulties, ABL, Primary School & Teachers

1. Introduction:

Education in India was through the Gurukul system up to a few centuries ago till the beginning of British rule in India. During the British rule, the British brought in their education system and started schools with the aim to prepare local Indian people for jobs in the British government in India. The Indian Education System has set high constitutional goals of Universalization of Elementary Education and Education for all. The Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, the flagship program of the Indian Government, has taken up the task of achieving universal elementary education in our country.

Educational commission reports and national debates form the basis of education reform and unfortunately educational research remains an underutilized area. Educational research is being undertaken by apex bodies of educational research such as NCERT and NUEPA or by the government itself such as the SSA and there is less of independent research in the field. Further, student achievements are studied more in terms of low levels of attainment such as ability of class V students to read class I or class II books. While it is disappointing that even at such low levels of expectations the results are so abysmal, they also allude to the fact that low expectations at all levels begets low quality at all levels. If after 93 amendments to our constitutional law, two major centralized programs and so many innovations, if India must serve its children's educational needs with high quality, the education system's reforms and innovations should be subjected to rigorous research. The evidence thus produced must serve with greater weightage as the basis for reforms in our education system. A shift in instructional methodology from traditional to any other method will be effective only if the methodology attends to certain important factors that can positively impact the education of the child and be in the best interest of the child. But in this ABL method transaction to the primary schools, teachers faced lot of problems. So the vestigator has identified the teachers working in the primary schools situated in cuddalore district as sample. Hence, the researcher has made an attempt to study the problems faced in activity based learning of the primary school teachers.

Primary School Teachers: The primary school teachers working in the school situated in Dharmapuri education district Tamil Nadu, India.

Problems Faced in Activity Based Learning: The Problems faced in Activity Based Learning of the selected sample of primary school teachers working in the schools, as revealed by the responses to the item in the problems faced in Activity Based Learning constructed and validated by K. Muruganantham (2010).

Objectives of the Present Study:

The following are the objectives of the study,

- To study the level of Difficulties faced by primary school teaches in Activity Based Learning.
- To study the significance of the difference between the following of sub-samples with respect to their problem faced in Activity Based leering
 - Gender (male/female)
 - Nature of family (nuclear / joint)
 - Age (upto 30 years /above 30 years)

2. Methodology:

This study is Normative surey method has been used for the study. Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning scale standardized by K. Muruganatham (2010) has been used to find out the Problems faced in Activity Based Learning of primary school teachers. It is taken from the school register. The tool was administered to a random sample of 250 primary school teachers working in the cuddalore education district. The scoring of the tool has been done according to the instructions given in the manual. The data has been subjected to statistical techniques like descriptive analysis and differential analysis.

3. Tool Used:

The following tool has been used for collecting data. Problems faced in Activity Based Learning scale standardized by K. Muruganatham (2010).

4. Analysis of Data:

Differential Analysis: It involves the most important procedure by which the researcher makes inferences between groups with reference to selected variables. It involves ‘t’ test and ‘F’ test. A ‘t’ test is a numerical procedures that takes into account, the size of the difference between the means of two groups the number subject in each group, and the quantum of variation of spread present in the scores. Thus the ‘t’ test us a teaching for determining whether the performance of two groups is significantly differential or not to determine whether there are significant difference among the means of more than two groups analysis of variance referred to a ANOVA is employed. The ANOVA yields the ‘F’ value. ‘F’ value is used to find out whether there are significant difference between the means of different groups. The hypotheses are tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation for Problems Faced in Activity Based Learning Scores

S.No	Sub-Sample	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	
1	Gender	Male	108	18.89	4.80
		Female	142	17.47	4.65
2	Nature of family	Nuclear	166	17.93	4.82
		joint	84	18.86	4.56
3	Age	Upto 30 years	105	17.22	4.44
		Above 30 years	145	18.97	4.82
4	Total Sample		250	18.24	4.74

It is evident from the table 4.1, that the computed mean value of the entire sample is 18.24 and S.D is 4.74. Hence it is found that the primary school teachers are facing high level of problem in ABL method.

Table 4.2: Comparison of the Means Problems Faced in ABL Scores of the Male and Female Primary School Teachers

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Male Teachers	108	18.89	4.80	1.91	Not Significant
Female Teachers	142	17.47	4.65		
Nuclear Family	166	17.93	4.82	1.51	Not Significant
Joint Family	84	18.86	4.56		
Upto 30 Years	105	17.22	4.44	5.54	Significant
Above 30 Years	145	18.97	4.82		

5. Discussions:

The difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores of primary school male and female teachers is significant or not, the null hypothesis that there is no such difference and the observed difference has arisen only due to change fluctuations has been set up. The ‘t’ value is found to be 1.91 which is not significant at 0.05 level (Table 4.2). It is concluded that the difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores of primary school male and female teachers is not significant. The difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores of primary school teachers from nuclear family and joint family is significant or not, the null hypothesis that there is no such difference and the observed difference has arisen only due to change fluctuations has been set up. The ‘t’ value is found to be 1.51 which is significant at 0.05 level . the difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores who belong to upto 30 years and above 30 years is significant or not, the null hypothesis that there is no such difference and the observed difference has arisen only due to change fluctuations has been set up. The ‘t’ value is found to be 5.54 which is significant at 0.05 level.

6. Findings:

The following are the important findings of the present study.

- Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning of primary school teachers is average. Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning of primary school teachers with respect to different sub-sample is average.
- Male and female primary school teachers do not differ significantly in their Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning.
- Primary school teachers belonging to differ in their nature of family do not differ significantly in their Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning.
- Primary school teachers who belong to upto 30 years and above 30 years differ significantly in their Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning.

7. Conclusions:

There is conclusion evidence in the study to show that the male and female primary school teachers do not differ significantly in their Difficulties faced in ABL. The difference between the mean Difficulties faced in ABL scores of primary school teachers from joint family and nuclear family is not significant and it is concluded that the difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores of primary school teaches who belongs to upto 30 years and above 30 years is significant.

8. References:

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